

MECHANICAL WEEDING IN PADDY CULTIVATION- A REVIEW

Kusuma Guturu^{1*}, Vipin P R²

Scientist (Agril. Engg.), Regional Agricultural Research Station, Anakapalle, ANGRAU, AP.
 Trainee Assistant Engineer, KAMCO Ltd., Athani, Ernakulam, Kerala, India.

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Abstract:

Weeding in paddy is one of the most labour inducive field operations, which need to be mechanized to improve the productivity of paddy crop and reduce the cost of cultivation. Many weeders are available for weeding in paddy cultivation viz., manually operated weeders, power operated weeders and autonomous weeders. In earlier days manually operated weeders viz., Cono weeder, Mandava weeder, Japanese weeder, star weeder gained importance because of their low cost. Later power operated weeders run with petrol or diesel engine, gained importance because of their higher field capacity compared to manually operated weeders. Autonomous or robotic weeders are now popular due to complete elimination of labour wading through puddled soil. All type of weeders from manually operated weeders to robotic weeders are discussed here with detailed photographs and their functions.

Key words: Paddy weeding, Mechanical weeders, Robotic weeders, Power weeders.

Introduction:

Paddy is cultivated all over the world, and it is a major food crop that feeds almost half of the world population. It is cultivated in 168.36 million hectares (Statista, 2025) in world with production of 540 million metric tonnes. India is the major contributor to the global rice production with annual production of 150 million metric tonnes from 46 million hectare of land (USDA stats, 2025). Weeds in paddy field is an important factor influences the yield of rice. Weed control in paddy fields is a worldwide problem and mechanical weeding will become a major weeding method in non-chemical weeding. (Chen et al., 2024). Weeding can be done by numerous ways viz., preventative, cultural, mechanical, chemical, biological or even biotechnological. Some of cultural methods of weed management in paddy fields include use of competitive cultivars. This is where a higher crop yielding variety competes with the weeds. Moisture management is also widely used since most weeds cannot germinate under flooded conditions. A mechanical weeder addresses the problem of labour shortage and decreasing income per acre while

reducing environmental degradation caused by herbicides. Selection of a weeding technique is purely based on improving efficiency, economics, environmental stewardship and soil conservation. Chemical weed control using herbicides has gained more popularity compared to the cultural and the mechanical methods. This is because herbicides tend to use less labour input and also they've been effective when there is shortage of labour for weeding during the critical periods. Besides being an effective way of weed management, major concerns have been raised on increased environmental pollution together with change of weed flora which has been attributed to continuous use of herbicides (Kathia et al. 2019).

Mechanical weeding is a friendly way to environment that helps to improve soil structure and increase soil fertility. Mechanical weeding not only favours the environment by eliminating herbicides use but also improves yield by 11-20% (Anonymous, 2006). These mechanical weeders are of four types viz., 1) Manually operated weeders 2) Power operated weeders 3) Autonomous weeders.

Manually operated Weeders:

Different types of manually operated weeders were developed by research institutes all over the world, mainly in Asian countries.

1. Cono weeder
2. Japanese weeder
3. Satr weeder
4. Mandava weeder
5. Kollur weeder
6. Raichur weeder
7. Tamilnadu weeder
8. English weeder
9. Four row weeder
10. Jharkhand weeder
11. Srilanka weeder
12. Nepal tarai weeder
13. Combodia weeder
14. Rotating hoe
15. Tefy saina weeder

Cono weeder:

It has two rotating cone shaped drums, with width adjustability. One drum rotates in clockwise direction and other runs in opposite direction. It is a push type weeder. It weighs nearly 7.5 kg. the cost ranges from Rs. 1500/- to Rs.2500/-

Fig.1. Cono weeder

Mandava weeder:

The float from the Cono-weeder, rod and handle from Kollur Weeder, the wheel from the Star Weeder and the mechanism to remove soil from the drum-plates in the Raichur weeder were integrated and adapted in designing a new weeder, which is now popularly known as Mandava Weeder. It weights nearly 5 kg. The cost of mandava weeder ranges from Rs.1000/- to Rs.1500/-

Fig. 2 Mandava weeder

Star weeder: It has cylindrical drum with spikes on its periphery. It is not provided with float. It is a light weight weeder costs around Rs.500/-

Fig. 3. Star weeder

Three row Raichur weeder: Three drums placed laterally to cover three rows with two handles, one to pull in the front and another push and steer from the back. Weeding in three rows will be completed in one go, hence saves labour and time. Two persons need to operate the weeder one to push the weeder from back and another to pull from front.

Fig. 4. Three row Raichur weeder

Power operated weeders:

Power operated weeders run through diesel or petrol engines having power range of 1-3 hp. The rotary blades are fitted in rows and get drive from the engine. The following are the different types of power operated weeders.

1. Garuda weeder
2. Japanese weeder
3. 4 row power weeder
4. Tractor mounted weeder

Garuda weeder:

It is two row weeder run with petrol engine of 1.4 kW. It has L type blades. A person operates the weeder as he walks in the field.

Fig. 5. Garuda weeder

Japanese weeder:

It is also a two row weeder runs with petrol or diesel engine having power of 1.4 kW. It has finger type blades to remove the weeds.

Fig. 6. Japanese weeder

Multi row power weeder: Multi row weeders covers more than two rows and is pushed by the operator at the back. As the weeders contain large width their field capacity is more. The maximum no. of rows in a weeder varies from 3 to 5. One person operates the weeders at the back. The drive is given to the front wheel.

Fig.7. Multi row power weeder

Tractor mounted weeder for paddy: tractor mounted weeders may be of stationary type, oscillating type and rotary type. These get drive from the tractor PTO. Tractor drawn weeders have higher field capacity than manually operated power weeders. Head land requirement is one of the major problem in running the tractor drawn weeders in Indian fields.

Autonomous/ Robotic weeders:

NAAS Rating – 04.17

Drudgery involved in operating manually operated weeders and power operated weeders was addressed by introduction of autonomous weeders. These weeders navigate autonomously by inbuilt programme or by remotely controlled from the operator. Many of these models are available and some are in developmental stage.

Robo Ducky:

Nakamura et al. 2016 developed robo ducky for churning of soil and water as the ducks in duck farming does. The soil and water churning does not allow the sunlight enter the soil thus preventing photosynthesis for the weeds. Hence a small and light weight robot which doesn't cause damage to the rice plants was developed and evaluated. The results showed that, it travels around the field for about three minutes. And it is possible for one robot to finish sweeping the whole field for thirty minutes. Additionally, the robot can locomote without overturn on the uneven surface and in paddy field with rice plant grows with a certain period. These results show that the robot has effectiveness for weeding in any pattern. Therefore, the new robot has high performance for weeding

Fig. 9. Principle of Duck weeding (Nakamura et al. 2016)

Fig. 10. The new robot locomote without overturn on the uneven surface.

Fig. 11. The robot can locomote without overturn in paddy field with rice plant grows with a certain period.

Weed control robot (K-Weedbot):

Choi et al. 2015, developed a robot which used a special type of wheel to remove the weeds while moving between rice rows, which were located under the center of the robot. The robot was equipped with screws instead of common wheels to ensure excellent performance on water-soaked soil, and a vision camera was mounted in front of the robot for image acquisition. The height (55 cm) and angle (30°) of the camera could be adjusted and were set based on the relationship between the robot and surface such that 2–3 rice rows could be detected in the image frame.

Fig. 12. Weed control robot in paddy fields (K-Weedbot) (a) robot configuration and (b) guidance line and auxiliary lines in paddy fields (Choi et al. 2015)

Japan paddy weeding robot:

Sori H, et al. 2018 developed a weeding robot for weeding in paddy. The experiment results showed that there was no weed growth in the weeded area, in which the weeding robot was operated. Furthermore, the rice plants in the weeded area displayed a larger growth in the roots, stems, and leaves compared with those in the unweeded area. Furthermore, after harvesting, the height of the rice plant, number of stems, and weight of the unhulled rice from the weeded area displayed substantially larger values compared with those for the unweeded area.

Fig. 13. Weeding robot (Sori, H. et al. 2018)

Roboduck:

Nissan has built a robot to help farmers reduce the use of herbicides and pesticides on their rice crops. The compact robot, called Aigamo, is designed to mimic the natural use of ducks that paddle around in flooded paddy fields.

Ducks have been used as natural weed repellents for centuries to tear them up and feed on insects, with their manure even acting as an additional fertilizer. It weighs 1.5 kg and is about the size of a large robot vacuum cleaner. Using two rotating rubber brushes on its underside which take the place of a duck's feet, it oxygenates the water by stirring it up and preventing weeds from taking root. It occupies an area of 60 cm² and it identifies its location mainly through GPS to navigate across rice paddies.

Fig. 14. AIGAMO robot (Nissan.com)

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